

Benedictine Order in Denmark

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As far as all the different monastic orders who were present in medieval Denmark are concerned, the Benedictine Order is particularly interesting as it seems to have been the very first monastic order to arrive in Denmark. The exact circumstances regarding when, where and how the order first arrived in Denmark fade into history, but it must have happened during the 11th C. The Benedictine monastery for monks in Odense, also serving as the holy chapter of Odense diocese, is known to have been founded by king Erik I Evergood of Denmark (1095-1103) no later than c. the second half of the 1090's. The only other monastic order potentially present in Denmark around that time, this early on, was the Augustinians. This order arrived no later than during the early 12th C. According to the tradition of Danish medieval annals from the c. 12/13th C., however, it was the christian viking king Cnut the Great (1018-1035) who was the first to bring monks to Denmark. At his time, Danish vikings had conquered England and Cnut thus served not only as king of Denmark, but also as king of England amongst other areas. Obviously, these annals were written only a very long time after events and any actual proof of this is therefore lacking, but there may be arguments in favor of believing in it. Firstly, it would seem to fit in rather well with knowledge of both Cnut's reign and of his acts as king of England. Secondly, the Benedictine monastery in Odense does not seem to be the first monastery in Denmark, thus the introduction of monks into Denmark must have happened already before the reign of Erik Evergood. Considering the 11th c. Danish kings before Erik, Cnut seems to be a likely candidate. One thing is that Cnut is believed to have been in active in organizing the early Danish diocesan structure and introducing also the concept of monasteries would thus have been a strong act logically attached to this work. Another thing is that his main successor as long-reigning king of Denmark during the 11th C., king Svend II Estridsøn (1047-1074/76), is known to have to been working intensely on not only reorganizing the Danish diocesan structure, but also on liberating the Danish church from the authority of the archdiocese of Hamburg-Bremen by getting papal permission to create an independent Danish archbishopric. This scheme did not succeed during his reign already, but question is whether his attempted plan would have been realistic and feasible at all if not even just a single monastery still existed in Denmark to support the diocesan structure and the available religious expertise present within the Danish church. Monasteries formed a very important part of the medieval church and imagining an independent Danish archbishopric without even just a single existing monastery would hardly be a realistic perspective in 11th C. Europe. This is something that Svend Estridsøn, as king and politician, would most likely have known also. Thus it should probably be believed that the first monasteries and monks, as a concept, were introduced into Denmark no later than during the reign of Svend Estridsøn and it is not unlikely that it could have happened already before that. As for Danish kings before Svend Estridsøn who could have done that, potentially, none other than Cnut the Great seems to be an obvious candidate for such an act. Talking about monasteries and monks in Denmark as early as the time of Cnut the Great and Svend Estridsøn, this would most likely have been Benedictine monks. This early on in Denmark, however, talking about any strong and firmly established monastic structure represented in any large numbers is absolutely unrealistic. Whether it was introduced by Cnut the Great or by Svend Estridsøn later on, at that time we are talking about only a single or a few monasteries at some very well-considered locations. Due to lack of sources on the early Danish monastic structure, it remains unknown which exact Benedictine monastery or monasteries that would have been the oldest one(s) in Denmark, but a few candidates can likely be nominated and the oldest Benedictine monastery in Denmark should probably be found amongst these candidates. Discussing the earliest Danish Augustinian convents thus must be a story for another time and this entry will therefore focus on the Benedictines exclusively. As the abovementioned Danish annals also indicate, the Benedictine monasteries for nuns should probably be ruled out when considering which

Danish monastery that possibly was the very first one in the country. Nunneries were generally introduced a little later than friaries in all the other monastic orders who were present in medieval Denmark, and there is no reason to believe that it would have been any different as regards the Benedictines. Also some of the benedictine monasteries for monks should probably be ruled out from such a discussion, as they seem to have been founded only later on. As far as candidates for identifying the very first Danish monastery are concerned, we are thus talking about identifying Danish Benedictine monasteries where signs can be found to make it seem likely that the monastery might perhaps have its roots of foundation during the 11th C. In addition to Odense there are only a few Danish Benedictine monasteries which seem even just potentially that old. Candidate no. 1 is Veng monastery in Jutland. Written sources on its early history say that it was founded and enriched by unspecified Danish kings well before the 1160's, but sources are otherwise absent. However, the monastery church is still preserved and this building is clearly both old and early. The most recent investigation suggests that it may have been built as early as the 1080's or perhaps later than that. However, this does not necessarily mean that the monastery was also founded only then. It seems to have been quite common that Danish monasteries used temporary wooden churches sometimes even for decades until the building of a stone church could be financed. So Veng monastery as an institution may actually have been older than the church building, although the exact age of Veng monastery remains hazy. Part of the explanation for this may be that it was closed already during the 12th C. and incorporated into the Cistercian monastery of Øm. Glenstrup monastery, also in Jutland, should probably be mentioned as candidate no. 2. The preserved monastery church seems likely to suggest that it may have been a quite early institution, although how early exactly is unknown as the early history also of this Benedictine monastery remains hazy due to lack of sources. It was later closed during the 15th C. and incorporated into the monastery of the bridgettines in Mariager. Candidate no. 3 must be the monastery of the benedictine monks in Lund in Scania which seems to have roots in the 11th C. as it was most likely founded between c. 1072/75 and 1089. The town of Lund became the site of the Danish archbishopric from the early 12th C. onwards, and the town thus seems to have become increasingly important already during the second half of the 11th C. which is why such an early monastery right here makes great sense. Candidates no. 4 and 5 are the two monasteries in Ringsted and Slagelse, respectively, both placed on Zealand. Both monasteries were apparently founded sometime between 1074 and 1088. The benedictine monastery in Ringsted evolved to become one of the most important monasteries of medieval Denmark. The monastery in Slagelse, however, is unknown to such an extent that it has been doubted whether it actually ever existed at all. There are, however, rather clear signs that it probably did. Its founding is spoken of directly by the Roskilde Chronicle and this piece of information in here is likely to have been based on the early archives of Roskilde diocese. A preserved medieval manuscript from around 1200, or perhaps from c. the first quarter of the 13th C., containing text by Pliny the Elder, also states that the manuscript was written by an otherwise unknown Danish man called Peter of Slagelse - most likely a monk. At that point in time in Denmark writing expertise at such a level would generally have been attached either to the dioceses and their holy chapters, to the royal court or to the monastic world. The manuscript therefore speaks in favor of the institution in Slagelse probably being an early benedictine monastery which was most likely closed no later than c. mid-13th C. Candidates no. 6, 7, and 8 must be the benedictine monasteries at either Slesvig, Seem, or perhaps Randers -all placed in Jutland. These monasteries become candidates as they all seem likely to have originated as double monasteries for both monks and nuns. This type of benedictine double monasteries, however, generally became obsolete after roughly 1100 or the early 1100s after which new ones were not really founded anymore and the existing ones were gradually dissolved - usually by either the monks or the nuns moving away to another newly established monastery instead. By originating as double monasteries these three institutions all suggest themselves as potentially quite early foundations, even despite the scarcity of sources. In Randers the monastery of the benedictine nuns perhaps originated as a double monastery until the monks moved away to Essenbæk monastery in the 12th C. Benedictine double monasteries are known with a far higher degree of certainty, though, from Slesvig and Seem. The monastery in Slesvig seems most likely to be the best candidate as for naming the oldest monastery in Denmark. It seems to have originated sometime during the 11th C. If it was founded either during the reign of Cnut the Great or perhaps a bit later on around 1050, during the early days of Svend Estridsøn, it would have been situated very near to Hedeby. This location would make great sense as

for the placing of such a very early monastery since Hedeby was one the most important towns of viking age Denmark and it thus also was an essential location for the Danish kings of that era. Despite the lack of written sources to support it, Cnut the Great having founded a benedictine monastery here could therefore easily be imagined. Another thing potentially speaking in favor of regarding the benedictines of Slesvig as inhabitants of the oldest monastery in Denmark is the fact that the 13th C. annals from Ryd monastery is the main source mentioning Cnut the Great as the very first to bring monks into Denmark. These annals were based on older source material and when the monastery of the benedictine monks in Slesvig was closed during the late 12th C., it ended up being incorporated into a Cistercian institution which soon evolved to become Ryd monastery. Ryd monastery thus was the successor institution of the benedictine friary in Slesvig and memorial traditions stemming from the predecessor institution could thus very well have seeped onwards through time into the successor institution until finally ending up in their written annals. If this assumption is correct it would speak in favor of the benedictine friary in Slesvig having been founded likely during the reign of Cnut the Great as, in all probability, the oldest monastery in Denmark. The benedictine order remained in Denmark until their monasteries were gradually closed after the Reformation. Their glory days, however, were pretty much over from c. the second half the 12th C. onwards after which other monastic orders took over and carried the banner of monastic fashion instead. From then on, a great number of Danish benedictine monasteries were either incorporated into monasteries of other orders or closed entirely and very few new ones were founded.

Date Range: 1018 CE - 1536 CE

Region: Early benedictine monasteries in Denmark

Region tags: Denmark

Those parts of Denmark where the monasteries mentioned in the text were placed.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Erik Kroman (publ.): Danmarks Middelalderlige Annaler, Selskabet for Udgivelse af Kilder til Dansk Historie, København 1980
- Source 2: Jørgen Olrik, Jacob Isager, H.N. Garner (transl.): Øm Klosters Krønike, Øm Kloster Museum, Øm 1997
- Source 3: Michael H. Gelting (transl): Roskildekrøniken, 2. edt., Wormanium, Højbjerg 2002

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://wiki.app.uib.no/medieval/index.php?title=Chronicon_Roskildense

Notes: Background information on the Roskilde Chronicle discussing usage of the capitular archives of Roskilde diocese. Article by Michael H. Gelting.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: not relevant

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Although elements of a yes answer could be argued.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– Yes

↳ Does the coercion take the form of physical force:

– No

↳ Does the coercion take the form of economic sanctions:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– No

Notes: But the king and the elite are heavy contributors to the financing of the monasteries.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– No

Notes: As above: not necessarily always, but the king and the elite were heavy contributors to the financing of the monasteries.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes yes, but not necessarily always

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Yes

Notes: to a limited extent, yes

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– Yes

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– Yes

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:
– Yes

↳ Punished in the afterlife:
– Yes

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:
– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:
– Yes

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):
– Yes

- ↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
- ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - No
 - Notes: although aspects of a yes to this question could sometimes probably also be argued
- ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - No
- ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:
 - No
 - Notes: aspects of a yes to this question could probably also be argued.
- ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Sometimes, not necessarily always
- ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - Yes
- ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– No

Notes: although sometimes probably yes.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: although sometimes perhaps yes.

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– No

Notes: although sometimes probably yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:
 - Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

- ↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: It varied, but in general the monastery churches took up a substantial area measured in percentage of the collective mass of monastery buildings.

- ↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

- ↳ Tombs:

– Yes

- ↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: monastery, monastery church

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

Notes: Within the order iconography was usual within the monastery churches, although not necessarily limited to the churches only.

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.
Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– I don't know

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No

- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
 - Notes: There is only one God, but the answer yes if the saints are regarded as supernatural beings being worshipped.

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No

↳ Other form of communication with living:
– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:
 - No
 - ↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Not necessarily, systematically, yes, but sometimes probably yes.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - No
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - No
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - No
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - No
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - No

- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - No
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - No
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - No
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - No
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - No

- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - No
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Notes: It depends on the nature of the rituals. If it was e.g. the translation event of a sanctified person such as it happened in both Odense and Ringsted monasteries it was a very rare event. Events such as such service and similar, happened in regular intervals.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– No

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Yes

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

↳ Other:

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Notes: Referring to the monks as brothers and the nuns as sisters.

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– No

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A monastic order

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: yes could perhaps also be argued?

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: knowledge of Danish nunneries is often poorer than knowledge of the friaries, comparatively, but as some medieval manuscripts are preserved also from Danish nunneries, these must have received such writing education somewhere.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:
– Yes

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:
– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:
– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: They used latin

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: But not necessarily the same calendar everywhere.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Also the brewing of beer is known from Danish monasteries.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that monasteries sometimes e.g. received food as tax payment from those local farmers whose lands were owned by monastery.

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